

BASIC APPROACH TECHNOLOGIES TO THE ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL PROCESSES IN GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *General secondary educational institutions, system, systematicity, integrity, pedagogical system, systematic approach technology, comprehensiveness, integrative, communicative, reflexive approach technology, person-active approach technology, coordinated approach technology, situational approach technology.*

Keywords: *general secondary educational institutions, system, systematicity, integrity, pedagogical system, systematic approach technology, comprehensiveness, integrativeness, communicativeness, reflexive approach technology, individual-active approach technology, coordinated approach technology, situational approach technology.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, all educational institutions have wide opportunities in such directions as choosing educational methods, making independent decisions in the organization and management of pedagogical processes, conducting an independent policy of the educational institution, and independently defining strategies for improving and developing pedagogical processes. is emerging. Currently, in the pedagogical processes organized by our state in educational institutions, students are taught to think independently and freely, to expand their worldview, to make the leaders of educational institutions and pedagogical staff capable, proactive, searching, enthusiastic, striving for success and achievers. Special attention is being paid to the issues of directing the formation of a spiritually mature person, that is, raising the quality level of the education system. Ensuring the effectiveness of pedagogical processes organized in general secondary educational institutions is unthinkable without the technology of a systematic approach to pedagogy. The introduction of such an approach serves to prevent accidental and unexpected situations in these processes. In the technology of the systematic approach, pedagogical processes organized in educational institutions, in particular, in general secondary educational institutions, are considered as an integral system of importance, that is, as a complex pedagogical system serving in the external environment. The main concept of the system approach technology is "system", which is represented by such concepts as communication, relationships, integration, integrity, constituent parts. A set of interrelated, interacting components of the system constitutes a single object.

In pedagogy, the concept of "system" is very widely used, for example, educational system, educational system, system of forms and methods of organizing the educational process, etc. Pedagogical system, which is one of the types of social system, consists of a set of various structurally and functionally related components that serve the purposes of education and upbringing of people and the young generation, organization and management of the educational process.

In pedagogy, there are different views in the direction of systematic approach technology, which include:

Systematicity, integrity - a system of this form is made up of interdependence and connection of components, interacting parts and joints, and their interconnection ensures the implementation and development of functional tasks.

In the pedagogical system, one of the factors that make up the system is the goal, and methods and tools are necessary to achieve it. The behavior of the system and its components in achieving the goal determines the essence of the system function.

Pedagogical system represents a set of components that make it up, and its change depends on internal conflicts.

Since the pedagogical system is open, it is connected with the external environment through many communications. The external environment and existing relations influence the movement and development of the pedagogical system.

Incoming and retransmitting information to the pedagogical system are methods of communication of the system components with each other and with the whole system, as well as the system with the external environment.

The main task of pedagogical staff and leaders in general secondary educational institutions is to develop pedagogical processes as a whole system in order to create the necessary conditions in the team to achieve positive results in the organization of pedagogical processes.

If we consider the pedagogical processes in general secondary educational institutions as an integrated system, their organization and management should also have a systematic nature. We can show the content and essence of the technology of a systematic approach to the analysis of the unique characteristics of pedagogical processes based on the following principles:

teachers and students, who are considered participants of the pedagogical process in general secondary educational institutions, act as subjects of this process, i.e. determine subject-subject relations in pedagogical processes;

goal orientation, consistency and interdependence of the activities of the subjects of the pedagogical process;

comprehensiveness - the fact that pedagogical processes are a set of interrelated and related components;

integrativeness - mutual unity of internal and external factors serving movement and development;

interdependence - the existence of pedagogical processes as a separate system and as a constituent component of a higher-order integrated pedagogical system;

communicativeness - the fact that the pedagogical system has the characteristics of interaction with the external environment and other systems [1].

The effectiveness of pedagogical processes in general secondary educational institutions, that is, the effectiveness of educational processes, determines the level of compliance of the subjects' personal development and training with the requirements of state educational standards. Pedagogical processes as a whole system develop based on internal changes and the system of mutual relations stabilizes. Tasks for achieving the goal, solving various problems are carried out using modern methods, the results are adapted to the requirements of the time, and the effectiveness of the pedagogical system is ensured.

An important component of the pedagogical system is the culture of the educational institution, which includes the technologies of the approach to solving existing problems in general secondary educational institutions, traditions, annuals, established procedures and standards. It will be necessary to harmonize the management, pedagogical, psychological and educational and spiritual processes of the general secondary educational institution.

In order to effectively organize and manage pedagogical processes in general secondary educational institutions, the internal management of the educational institution, that is, internal control, consisting of leaders and other representatives of the team, is organized. The team of an educational institution is a complex system, consisting of formal and informal, horizontal and vertical, interpersonal and interpersonal factors that influence the satisfactory organization of educational and work activities, as well as the results of the educational institution. It covers relations and relations related to labor activity.

In pedagogical processes, the reflexive approach technology is of special importance as an important mechanism of their independent and effective thinking in coordinating the activities of subjects. In the process of reflexive approach technology, separate organization of the processes of explaining the concepts studied in the context of a wide system, evaluating the situations and behavior of the subjects, determining the methods and directions of effective performance of the assigned tasks, self-analysis of the subjects, creates conditions for him to actively think about his concepts and actions.

In the organization and management of pedagogical processes, the technology of the person-active approach is considered necessary, and it is created as a direction to ensure the activity of subjects in pedagogical processes and motivate subjects to perform tasks set according to specific goals.

In the technology of the person-activity approach, the components of the person and the activity are studied in close connection with each other, because in the pedagogical processes organized on the basis of this approach technology, students act as subjects and, in turn, the development of the student's personality as a subject is determined by the development of his activity, independent, free, critical, analytical and effective thinking.

The rapidly changing characteristics of pedagogical processes and the activity of subjects determine the need to focus on the introduction of another methodological approach technology, that is, to determine the best method of management depending on the internal and external situation of the managed object in a given situation. This, in turn, implies the application of the situational approach technology to the organization and management of pedagogical processes.

Situational approach technology - provides for determining the effectiveness of the pedagogical process according to specific situations. One of the most effective ways is to coordinate and manage the activities of subjects according to the emerging situations.

Coordinating the activities of subjects - pupils-pupils, depending on the internal and external situation of the pedagogical process, which is considered a managed object in the situational approach technology, serves to ensure the effectiveness of this process. In the process of situational approach technology, it is important to take into account the following:

- to study, analyze and objectively assess the situations that arise in the pedagogical process in order to determine the factors that are important in the improvement of pedagogical processes;

- determining in advance the effectiveness of the results that can be achieved in various pedagogical situations;
- determining ways to ensure the activity of subjects on the basis of pre-imagining the factors affecting this process and the situations that may arise in planning the organization of pedagogical processes and activities of subjects on a scientific basis.

CONCLUSION

To increase the efficiency of pedagogical processes, to ensure that the costs involved in ensuring the activity of subjects in achieving the intended goal do not exceed the norm, and are compatible with the possibilities, abilities and initial concepts of subjects, as well as existing situations and conditions. , to create a system that is most convenient and able to reorganize the pedagogical process and its structural structure is the introduction of a coordinated approach technology.

Simply put, as a result of the implementation of the coordinated approach technology, labor and time spent on ensuring the activity of subjects and the effectiveness of the pedagogical process are saved, as well as one-sidedness in the pedagogical processes, that is, only the teacher as a subject zi operation is eliminated.

Figure 1. Basic technologies of organization and management of pedagogical processes.

The concept of management based on results is valid as a development system, and it is possible to achieve the specified results based on coordinating the activities of the subjects of the pedagogical process and ensuring their activity. In this process, self-management of the subjects and the introduction of creative approach technology to their activities are ensured by explaining the essence of the tasks and concepts to be learned to each participant.

Based on the information presented above, taking into account the interdependence and relevance of the technologies of organization and management of pedagogical processes in general secondary educational institutions, they are conditionally considered as the main technologies of organization and management of pedagogical processes (Fig. 1) can be described.

Because none of the technologies presented in the organization and management of pedagogical processes can independently claim universality in voluntary situations. Therefore, it is appropriate to use them interdependently in the voluntary pedagogical process.

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